

Formation of Binary, Binucleating and Mixed Metal Complexes of Catechol Violet

POONAM UPADHYA, MAMTA SINGH, RASHMI VIMAL and RAM NAYAN*

Department of Chemistry, Hindu College, Moradabad-244 001

Manuscript received 16 June 1995, revised 15 February 1996, accepted 8 March 1996

pH-metric studies on interaction of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Pd^{II}, Ag^I and Cd^{II} with 3, 4', 4'-trihydroxyfuchsome-2''-sulphonic acid (catechol violet, CAV) have been carried out in aqueous solution at 25° and an ionic strength of 0.1 M KNO₃. Studies reveal the formation of the species MH₂A, MHA, MA (M = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Pd^{II}, Ag^I and Cd^{II}); PdA(OH)⁻; M(H₂A)₂, M(H₂A)(HA), M(HA)₂ (M = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}); M(HA)(A) (M = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}); M₂A (M = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Pd^{II}, Cd^{II}); M₂A(OH) (M = Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Pd^{II}, Cd^{II}); M₂A(OH)₂ (M = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}); CuNiA, CuZnA; PdNiA, PdCuA, PdZnA, CuNiA(OH), CuZnA(OH), PdZnA(OH), CuNiA(OH)₂, CuZnA(OH)₂ in the corresponding metal-ligand mixtures for which equilibrium constants have been evaluated.

The hydroxytriphenylmethane compounds, including catechol violet (CAV), are the class of organic dyes which are of great significance to their uses in the detection and determination of a large number of cations and anions¹ and in biological fields². Further behaviour of polydentate ligands is particularly interesting to form different species with a particular transition metal ion³. Generally CAV forms binary species including some protonated and mixed protonated hydroxo complexes^{4,5}, and the existence of only a few binucleating complexes in solution has also been inferred⁶.

In present work interactions of the Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Pd^{II}, Ag^I, Cd^{II} separately and in pairs, with CAV have been investigated in aqueous solution. Formation of different binary, binucleating and mixed metal complexes has been inferred by analysis of pH vs *a* curves⁷. Concentrations of binary protonated and hydroxo species and the corresponding stability constant in 1 : 1 metal-ligand systems have been calculated. In the case of protonated 1 : 2, metal-ligand and binucleating equilibria the concentration of the complex species and their equilibrium constant have been

obtained by new expressions derived from mass and charge balance relations⁷.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand dissociation : The pH vs *a* curve of CAV lies between *a* = 1 and 3 in the pH range 2.8–11.0 (Fig. 1). The colour of CAV solution is red between pH 2.8 and 6.6 which is due to deprotonated sulphonic acid group (H₃A⁻ species, Table 1). The proton-ligand dissociation constant corresponding to SO₃H group could not be evaluated due to its complete ionisation below initial experimental pH 2.8. The value of *a* remains constant (*a* = 1.0) between pH 2.80 and 6.10. The colour of the titration mixture slowly turns violet to deep violet from pH 6.7 to 8.9. Here, dissociation of proton from phenolic group adjacent to C=O forming the violet species H₂A²⁻ is expected. The proton-ligand dissociation constant for the equilibrium evaluated by the earlier described method is 10^{-7.87 ± 0.05}. Further, The violet colour gradually changes to green from pH ~9.0 (*a* ~2.0). Thus, between *a* = 2 and 3 the formation of green species (HA³⁻) as a result of proton dissociation from the another phenolic group is expected in solution.

Here, it has been noted that the pH-meter readings are unstable beyond pH ~10.2 probably due to oxidation of the ligand in highly alkaline range. Thus, *a* values above pH 10.2 have not be considered for calculation of equilibrium constants. The proton-ligand dissociation constant values obtained in the present investigation ($K_2^H = 10^{-7.87 \pm 0.05}$ and $K_3^H = 10^{-9.93 \pm 0.02}$) are in good agreement with those reported by Biryuk and Ravitaskaya ($K_2^H = 10^{-7.90}$, $K_3^H = 10^{9.94}$ at 25°, $\mu = 0.1$ M NaClO₄)⁴.

Metal-ligand complexes :

1 : 1, Metal-CAV complexes : The colour of 1 : 1, Ni^{II}-CAV mixture is red below pH ~4.1. A gradual change from red to green between pH ~4.5 and 6.8 (*a* = 2.0) in addition to a weak inflection in pH vs *a* curve at *a* = 2, indicates formation of MH₂A species. The colour of the mixture gradually turns blue from pH 6.8 to 8.8 (*a* = 3.0). A sharp inflection in pH vs *a* curve at *a* = 3.0, indicates that near this *a* value the blue MHA species exists independently.

Intensity of the blue colour remains nearly unchanged beyond $a = 3.0$. But the titration curve shows that complete deprotonation of the NiHA^- takes place above $\text{pH} \sim 8.8$. Corresponding equilibrium constants for reactions are given in Table 1. In the pH range of coordination of OH^- ions with the non-protonated species NiA (beyond $\text{pH} 10.2$) neither any calculation nor analysis of titration curve was possible due to ligand decomposition.

Formation of CuH_2A takes place below $\text{pH} \sim 4.6$ ($a \sim 2.0$) as indicated by the colour change of the mixture from red to brown up to $\text{pH} 4.4$ ($a = 1.75$) and a weak inflection in pH vs a curve at $a \sim 2.0$ (Fig. 1). Further deviation of pH vs a curve and appearance of blue colour in the titration mixture from $\text{pH} \sim 4.5$ ($a \sim 1.9$) show the deprotonation of the complex into CuHA^- and CuA^{2-} below $\text{pH} \sim 9.5$ ($a \sim 4$). The equilibrium constants calculated for the reaction are given in Table 1. Existence of ZnH_2A is indicated by a weak inflection in pH vs a curve of the system and also by the gradual colour change from red to green. The green colour is visible from $\text{pH} \sim 5.30$, while the complex formation occurs from $\text{pH} \sim 4.0$. A change in colour between $a = 2$ and 3 , from green to blue shows the formation of monoprotonated complex ZnHA^- . A sharp inflection in pH vs a curve (figure omitted) at $a = 3.0$ and further increase in a value indicate deprotonation of ZnHA^- with no interference of diprotonated complex. Titration curve for 1 : 1, Pd^{II} -CAV system indicates two weak inflections at $a = 2$ and 3 and a sharp inflection at $a = 4$. Thus, below $a = 2$, the formation of PdH_2A may be expected similar to the metal systems described earlier. The reaction mixture shows that

the diprotonated complex is brown. During deprotonation of the diprotonated species into monoprotonated PdHA^- , the brown colour remains unchanged. The titration mixture gradually changes to blackish green from $\text{pH} \sim 5.6$ ($a = 2.8$). This colour is expected due to the existence of PdA^{2-} complex. Appearance of the colour just below $a = 3.0$ is due to the coexistence of PdHA^- and PdA^{2-} complexes as also indicated by the weak inflection in the titration curve at $a \sim 3.0$. Beyond $a \sim 3.0$, the colour of the mixture (blackish green) does not change while the a values increase up to 4.3 . Here, formation of $\text{Pd}(\text{OH})^{3-}$ may be expected. Colour of the Ag^{I} -CAV mixture gradually changes to brown from red between $a \sim 0$ and 1.85 . A light yellowish green colour appears at $\text{pH} \sim 4.8$ ($a \sim 1.85$). The colour finally changes to dark yellowish green at $\text{pH} \sim 7.0$ ($a \sim 3.0$). Beyond $a = 3.0$, the colour of the mixture gradually turns yellowish brown. A comparison of the colour changes in different pH ranges with the weak and sharp inflections at $a = 2$ and 3 in pH vs a curve, shows that AgH_2A^- , AgHA^{2-} and AgA^{3-} complexes are brown, yellowish green and yellowish brown respectively. The colour of 1 : 1, Cd^{II} -CAV mixture is red below $\text{pH} \sim 4.5$. It gradually changes to yellowish green between $\text{pH} \sim 4.5$ and 6.7 ($a = 2$), blue between $\text{pH} \sim 7.0$ and 8.2 ($a = 3.0$) and blackish blue beyond $a = 3.0$. Thus the yellowish green, blue and blackish blue colours are expected due to the formation of CdH_2A^- , CdHA^- and CdA^{2-} complexes respectively. The equilibrium constants for the reactions are given in Table 1.

Table 1 indicates that the chelating tendency of CAV, in the formation of all the species, MH_2A , MHA and MA

TABLE 1—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS (log K) OF METAL-CAV COMPLEXES

Temp. = 25°, $\mu = 0.1 \text{ M}$ (KNO_3)

Reaction*

	Ni^{II}	Cu^{II}	Zn^{II}	Pd^{II}	Ag^{I}	Cd^{II}
$\text{M} + \text{H}_2\text{A} \rightleftharpoons \text{MH}_2\text{A}$	5.35 ± 0.06	6.97 ± 0.06	5.71 ± 0.04	8.29 ± 0.05	7.23 ± 0.07	5.23 ± 0.05
$\text{M} + \text{HA} \rightleftharpoons \text{MHA}$	8.30 ± 0.04	12.47 ± 0.07	8.92 ± 0.12	13.67 ± 0.10	11.51 ± 0.11	8.18 ± 0.02
$\text{M} + \text{HA} \rightleftharpoons \text{MA} + \text{H}^+$	-2.21 ± 0.04	5.32 ± 0.13	-0.54 ± 0.15	6.42 ± 0.07	2.12 ± 0.10	-1.79 ± 0.08
$\text{MH}_2\text{A} + \text{H}_2\text{A} \rightleftharpoons \text{M}(\text{H}_2\text{A})_2$	4.79 ± 0.02	6.43 ± 0.16	5.29 ± 0.04	—	—	4.43 ± 0.02
$\text{M} + 2\text{H}_2\text{A} \rightleftharpoons \text{M}(\text{H}_2\text{A})(\text{HA}) + \text{H}^+$	3.22 ± 0.24	7.80 ± 0.12	4.25 ± 0.13	—	—	2.71 ± 0.07
$\text{M} + 2\text{HA} \rightleftharpoons \text{M}(\text{HA})_2$	13.56 ± 0.11	19.56 ± 0.16	15.70 ± 0.13	—	—	13.64 ± 0.13
$\text{M} + 2\text{HA} \rightleftharpoons \text{M}(\text{HA})(\text{A}) + \text{H}^+$	—	9.43 ± 0.09	5.69 ± 0.13	—	—	3.24 ± 0.34
$\text{MA} + \text{OH}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{MA}(\text{OH})$	—	—	—	3.60 ± 0.14	—	—
$2\text{M} + \text{HA} \rightleftharpoons \text{M}_2\text{A} + \text{H}^+$	3.91 ± 0.09	10.08 ± 0.14	6.22 ± 0.02	15.91 ± 0.11	—	4.95 ± 0.09
$\text{M}_2\text{A} + \text{OH}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{M}_2\text{A}(\text{OH})$	—	7.88	6.80	8.25	—	5.80
$\text{M}_2\text{A}(\text{OH}) + \text{OH}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{M}_2\text{A}(\text{OH})_2$	—	—	6.40	—	—	4.61
$\text{CuH}_2\text{A} + \text{M} \rightleftharpoons \text{CuMA} + 2\text{H}^+$	-7.71 ± 0.04	—	-7.15 ± 0.04	—	—	—
$\text{CuMA} + \text{OH}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{CuMA}(\text{OH})$	6.40	—	6.90	—	—	—
$\text{CuMA}(\text{OH}) + \text{OH}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{CuMA}(\text{OH})_2$	4.85	—	6.40	—	—	—
$\text{PdH}_2\text{A} + \text{M} \rightleftharpoons \text{PdMA} + 2\text{H}^+$	-8.04 ± 0.04	-5.84 ± 0.04	-8.36 ± 0.02	—	—	—
$\text{PdMA} + \text{OH}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{PdMA}(\text{OH})$	—	—	6.25	—	—	—

* Charges omitted for simplicity.

with the metal ions of the first and second transition series Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and Pd^{II} , Ag^{I} , Cd^{II} respectively, follow the order : $\text{Ni}^{\text{II}} < \text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$ and $\text{Pd}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ag}^{\text{I}} > \text{Cd}^{\text{II}}$. From an observation on proton dissociation from the complexes the above order for acidic nature of their metal complexes is also evident.

1 : 2, Metal-CAV complexes : The colour of 1 : 2 Ni^{II} -CAV mixture at initial pH values is red. Deviation of pH vs a curve of this system in the right direction from the corresponding composite curve of ligand and the 1 : 1 metal-ligand system, and a gradual colour change in the mixture from red to yellowish green between pH ~4.7 and 6.7, indicate the formation of $\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{A})_2$ complex. In this pH range, the colour of the ligand and the 1 : 1, metal-ligand complex are red/violet and green respectively. A gradual colour change to green up to pH ~7.8 ($a \sim 2.5$) and a sharp inflection in pH vs a curve at $a \sim 2.5$ indicate that the green colour is due to existence of $\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{A})(\text{HA})$. Beyond $a = 2.5$, the colour of the mixture turns blue where formation of $\text{Ni}(\text{HA})_2$ may be expected.

New expressions were derived using mass and charge balance relation⁷ for free ligand and the complex species concentration between different ranges of a values considering existence of $\text{MH}_2\text{A} + \text{M}(\text{H}_2\text{A})_2$; $\text{M}(\text{HA})_2 + \text{M}(\text{H}_2\text{A})_2 + \text{M}(\text{H}_2\text{A})(\text{HA})$; $\text{MH}_2\text{A} + \text{M}(\text{H}_2\text{A})_2 + \text{M}(\text{H}_2\text{A})(\text{HA}) + \text{M}(\text{HA})_2$; respectively, between $a = 2$ and 2.5 ; $a = 2.5$ and 3 ; $a = 3.0$ and 3.57 .

Formation of $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{A})_2$ is indicated by a comparison of composite titration curve of CAV and 1 : 1 metal-CAV system with titration curve of 1 : 2, metal-CAV system, and also by colour change in titration mixture. The colour of the solution is red below pH ~3.1, which changes to brown from pH ~3.1 to 3.7 where formation of CuH_2A is expected. There is further change to green between pH ~4.7 and 5.5 ($a \sim 2.0$). Appearance of green colour below $a = 2.0$ supports the formation of 1 : 2, Cu^{II} -CAV complex. The titration mixture gradually turns blue from pH 5.9 to 10.2 with no further colour change. It indicates that all protonated complexes, $\text{CuH}_3\text{A}_2^{3-}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{HA})_2^{4-}$ and CuHA_2^{5-} , except $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{A})_2^{2-}$ are blue. The corresponding values of equilibrium constant other than K_2 ($[\text{M}(\text{H}_2\text{A})_2]/[\text{MH}_2\text{A}][\text{H}_2\text{A}]$) were evaluated using the equations derived for Ni^{II} system. For calculation of K_2 , existence of CuHA^- , which is formed at very low pH values, has also been considered in mass and charge balance relations used. In other systems, consideration of only one 1 : 1, metal-ligand complex MH_2A along with 1 : 2, metal-ligand species yield the result. From comparison of pH vs a curves of CAV, 1 : 1 and 1 : 2, Zn^{II} -CAV system and colour change from red to green between pH ~5.6 and 6.8 ($a \sim 2.0$), existence of $\text{Zn}(\text{H}_2\text{A})_2^{2-}$ is expected. Change in colour from green to blue (pH 6.9–7.6) indicates formation of $\text{Zn}(\text{H}_2\text{A})\text{HA}^{3-}$ between $a = 2$ and 2.5 . There is no further colour change. However, formation of other protonated species is evident from increase

TABLE 2 –MAXIMUM %M DISTRIBUTED AMONG VARIOUS SPECIES*

Temp. = 25°, $\mu = 0.1 \text{ M}$ (KNO_3)		Maximum %M distributed/(pH)					
Metal-ligand system	Species	Ni^{II}	Cu^{II}	Zn^{II}	Pd^{II}	Ag^{I}	Cd^{II}
1 : 1	M	91.07(4.8)	88.00(3.6)	88.14(4.6)	64.00(2.8)	70.00(3.8)	97.02(4.4)
	MH_2A	82.09(6.6)	74.98(4.4)	57.50(6.2)	80.00(3.6)	84.99(4.8)	79.98(6.6)
	MHA	94.40(8.4)	93.08(5.8)	92.52(7.8)	93.79(5.8)	97.31(7.2)	91.93(8.0)
	MA	30.12 (10.2)	90.01(9.2)	80.02(10.2)	94.99(8.4)	84.99 (10.2)	68.09(10.2)
1 : 2	M	64.83(5.6)	11.77(4.8)	74.95(5.0)	–	–	51.66(6.0)
	MH_2A	47.21(6.2)	25.13(4.8)	46.85(6.0)	–	–	56.14(6.6)
	$\text{M}(\text{H}_2\text{A})_2$	54.58(6.8)	57.58(5.4)	49.00(6.4)	–	–	75.66(7.2)
	$\text{M}(\text{H}_2\text{A})(\text{HA})$	88.85(7.8)	93.00(6.8)	69.40(7.6)	–	–	88.63(8.0)
	$\text{M}(\text{HA})_2$	87.88(10.2)	93.36(9.2)	80.20(9.2)	–	–	88.26(9.8)
	$\text{M}(\text{HA})(\text{A})$	–	54.43(10.2)	75.99(10.2)	–	–	50.98(10.2)
2 : 1	M	50.80(7.0)	39.77(5.0)	56.00(6.0)	35.07(3.2)	–	62.96(6.2)
	MH_2A	20.14(7.0)	28.41(5.0)	36.85(6.0)	14.81(3.2)	–	33.25(6.2)
	M_2A	41.93(7.8)	76.27(5.8)	81.11(7.0)	95.23(4.0)	–	87.90(7.6)
MCuA (1 : 1 : 1)	M	93.64(5.6)	–	72.14(5.8)	–	–	–
	MCuA	57.45(7.0)	–	85.60(6.8)	–	–	–
MPdA (1 : 1 : 1)	M	92.78(6.0)	88.28(4.2)	73.09(7.0)	–	–	–
	MPdA	49.44(7.4)	85.27(5.8)	48.86(6.8)	–	–	–

*Under experimental pH conditions.

in a value up to $a \sim 3.3$. Attempts to study to 1 : 2, metal-CAV equilibria for Pd^{II} and Ag^{I} systems were unsuccessful as the composite pH vs a curves of ligand and 1 : 1, metal-CAV systems almost coincides with that of the corresponding 1 : 2, metal-ligand systems. In Cd^{II} system, an identical colour change (red-green) below pH ~ 6.1 with that 1 : 1, metal-ligand system has been noted. From comparison of the pH vs a curves and appearance of weak inflection in the titration curve of 1 : 2, metal-ligand system at $a = 2.0$, existence of $\text{Cd}(\text{H}_2\text{A})_2^{2-}$ species is inferred. The colour of the mixture remains blue beyond pH ~ 7.0 ($a \sim 2.0$). From the shape of the titration curve formation of $\text{CdH}_3\text{A}_2^{3-}$, $\text{CdH}_2\text{A}_2^{4-}$ and CdHA_2^{3-} is expected between pH ~ 7.0 and 10.2.

A comparison of K_2 values (Table 1) indicates that the attachment of second molecule of the ligand species, H_2A^{2-} and HA^{3-} with the MH_2A and MHA respectively, follow the order : $\text{CuH}_2\text{A} > \text{ZnH}_2\text{A} > \text{NiH}_2\text{A} > \text{CdH}_2\text{A}$ and $\text{CuHA}^- > \text{ZnHA}^- > \text{CdHA}^- > \text{NiHA}^-$.

2 : 1, Metal-CAV complexes : Deviation of pH vs a curve of 2 : 1, Ni^{II} -CAV system (figure omitted) from that of 1 : 1 system from a low pH value (pH ~ 4.0) is due to increased metal ion concentration in solution leading to the formation of 1 : 1, metal-ligand species in considerable amount. An appreciable shifting of this curve from pH ~ 6.5 ($a \sim 2$) may be expected as the result of attachment of second metal ion with the ligand. The colour of the mixture is identical with that of 1 : 1 Ni^{II} -CAV system throughout the experimental range of pH, except appearance of light turbidity (blue) between pH ~ 8.0 and 10.2. Thus, for the equilibrium, $2\text{M} + \text{HA} \rightleftharpoons \text{M}_2\text{A} + \text{H}^+$; $K = [\text{M}_2\text{A}][\text{H}^+]/[\text{M}]^2[\text{HA}]$ (existing between $a = 2$ and 4), K value was evaluated by expressions (1)–(3) derived using mass and charge balance equations considering the presence of $[\text{M}]$, $[\text{NiH}_2\text{A}]$, $[\text{NiHA}]$, $[\text{Ni}_2\text{A}]$ in solution,

$$(4x_1x_3 - a_2\lambda_2)[\text{HA}]^2 + (a_2 + x_2\lambda_4)[\text{HA}] - x_4 = 0 \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. pH vs a curve of CAV complexes with Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} .

$$[\text{M}] = 2a_1 [\text{HA}]/(1 - x_2)[\text{HA}] \quad (2)$$

$$[\text{M}_2\text{A}] = C_{\text{M}} - [\text{M}] - [\text{MH}_2\text{A}] - [\text{MHA}] \quad (3)$$

where,

$$a_1 = [\text{H}^+]^2/K_2^{\text{H}}K_3^{\text{H}} + [\text{H}^+]/K_3^{\text{H}} + 1, \quad a_2 = 3[\text{H}^+]^2/K_2^{\text{H}}K_3^{\text{H}} + 2[\text{H}^+]/K_3^{\text{H}} + 1, \quad x_1 = K_1a_1[\text{H}^+]/K_3^{\text{H}}$$

$$x_2 = K_4[\text{H}^+]/K_3^{\text{H}} + K'_1, \quad x_3 = 2K'_1a_3, \quad K'_1 = [\text{MHA}]/[\text{M}][\text{HA}], \quad x_4 = C_{\text{A}}(4 - a),$$

$$a_3 = 2.5[\text{H}^+]^2/K_2^{\text{H}}K_3^{\text{H}} + 1.5[\text{H}^+]/K_3^{\text{H}} + 0.5$$

In the Cu^{II} system as expected, below $a = 2.0$ the colour change in the titration mixture is identical with that of 1 : 1, Cu^{II} -CAV system. But appearance of blue colour between $a = 2.0$ and 4.0 and a weak inflection in the pH vs a curve (figure omitted) indicate formation of binucleating complex Cu_2A . Formation of Zn_2A is indicated by comparison of pH vs a curve of 1 : 1 and 2 : 1, metal-ligand system, and in addition by gradual colour change in reaction mixture from yellowish green to green between pH 5.8 and 7.0 ($a = 4$). From pH ~ 7.0 , the colour of the mixture turns blue, which persists up to pH 10.2. Here formation of hydroxo complexes is evident beyond pH ~ 7.0 from the colour change as well as the shape of the titration curve (Fig. 1). Formation of 2 : 1, Pd^{II} -CAV complex (M_2A , brown) between pH 2.8 and 4.0 is shown by the corresponding titration curve. The colour of the solution changes from brown to brownish green in the pH range 4.0–8.4 (a 4–5). It indicates formation of anionic hydroxo complex $\text{Pd}_2(\text{OH})\text{A}^-$. A dark blue precipitate appears in the mixture above pH ~ 8.6 . The pH-meter readings for Ag^{I} -CAV system are unstable below pH ~ 8.0 . In addition, the titration mixture remains turbid throughout the experimental pH. Hence, no information could be achieved on the equilibrium reactions of the binucleating complex. Formation of M_2A species is concluded in 2 : 1, Cd^{II} -CAV mixture on the basis of titration curve comparison. A colour change from green to blue at pH 6.7–7.8 ($a \sim 4.0$) shows that the Cd_2A is blue colour species. Beyond $a = 4$ (below pH ~ 10.2) the mixture remains without any further change in colour.

From the above discussion it is concluded that the coordination behaviour of the metal ions with their corresponding 1 : 1, metal-ligand species, forming neutral binucleating M_2A complex, follows the trend : $\text{Pd}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cd}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$.

Mixed metal-CAV complexes : In 1 : 1, metal-CAV mixture, the pH range of the formation of CuH_2A (brown), NiH_2A (green), ZnH_2A (green), PdH_2A (brown), CdH_2A (yellowish green) are 3.3–4.6, 4.5–6.8, 4.6–6.5, 2.8–3.8, 4.6–6.7 respectively. Thus, for formation of M-M'-CAV type mixed metal binucleating complex in a corresponding metal and ligand mixture, coordination of Pd^{II} and Cu^{II} with CAV to yield MH_2A may be considered as first step

reaction Further attachment of Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} with PdH_2A and Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} with CuH_2A may be expected to occur in second step ($\text{MH}_2\text{A} + \text{M}' \rightleftharpoons \text{MM}'\text{A} + 2\text{H}^+$, $k = [\text{MM}'\text{A}][\text{H}^+]^2/[\text{MH}_2\text{A}][\text{M}']$) For investigating the equilibrium related to $\text{MM}'\text{A}$ type species involving the aforesaid system, it has been assumed that metal-metal exchange does not take place in the pH range of coordination of second metal (M') with MH_2A

The 1 : 1 : 1, Cu^{II} - Ni^{II} -CAV mixture remains brown below pH ~4.5 ($a \sim 2.0$) probably due to presence of CuH_2A complex. The colour of the mixture gradually changes to blue from pH 4.5 to 7.0 ($a = 3.8$). Appearance of the blue colour is expected due to the existence of CuNiA . Formation of this mixed metal complex is also evident from the inflection in pH vs a curve at $a = 4.0$. The equilibrium constant value for the binucleating complex was calculated similar to 1 : 1, metal-CAV system involving $[\text{Ni}^{2+}]$, $[\text{CuH}_2\text{A}]$, $[\text{CuHA}^-]$, $[\text{CuA}^{2-}]$ into mass and charge balance relations. The blue colour persists upto pH 10.2. Between pH ~7.0 and 10.2, presence of hydroxo complexes is also indicated by the titration curve. The titration curve for 1 : 1 : 1, Cu^{II} - Zn^{II} -CAV mixture shows an inflection at $a = 4.0$ and also deviates from the corresponding curve of 1 : 1, Cu^{II} -CAV system from pH ~4.6. A colour change from brown to blue between pH 4.6 ($a = 2.0$) and 6.2 ($a = 3.8$) confirms the existence of the mixed metal binucleating complex. The colour of the mixture further changes gradually from blue to greenish blue between pH 6.8 ($a = 4.0$) and 10.2. The greenish blue colour provides an additional evidence for existence of new species in the mixture as both the 1 : 1, metal-CAV mixture of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} are blue at higher pH values.

Deviation of pH vs a curve of Pd^{II} -CAV system from the corresponding curve of 1 : 1, Pd^{II} -CAV system from pH 3.9 indicates the formation of PdCuA complex. However, the species is not independently formed as indicated by the pH vs a curve which does not show an inflection at $a = 4.0$. But change in colour of mixture from brown to greenish brown between pH 3.8 ($a = 2.0$) and 5.9 ($a = 3.9$) supports the formation of the binucleating mixed metal complex. At pH 6.0 ($a = 4.0$) the mixture turns turbid (dull blue colour) and finally at pH 10.2 it yields a thick precipitate.

The brown colour of Pd^{II} - Ni^{II} -CAV mixture (due to presence of PdH_2A) gradually changes to green from pH 5.5 to 7.1 ($a = 3.7$). Subsequently at pH 7.3 ($a = 3.8$) a blackish blue colour appears which may be expected due to existence of hydroxo complex present in small amount. The mixture yields blackish blue precipitate at pH 7.4 ($a = 3.9$). The amount and the colour of the precipitate persist even at higher experimental pH values. Formation of PdZnA (blue) complex is also evident from the corresponding titration curve. Zn^{II} gets attached with PdH_2A at pH

Fig 2 Distribution of Zn^{II} in 1 : 1 : 1 : 2 : 2 : 1 metal-CAV and 1 : 1 : 1 metal Cu^{II} CAV mixture (—) 1 : 1 (---) 1 : 2 (---) 2 : 1 and (· · ·) 1 : 1 : 1 metal CAV and metal Cu^{II} -CAV mixture temp = 25° , $\mu = 0.1 \text{ M}$ (KNO_3)

6.1–7.4. The equilibrium constant was calculated as usual. It was not possible to record the equilibrium constant value for its hydroxo complexes as existence of dark blue precipitate in the reaction mixture beyond pH ~7.5 ($a = 4.0$) did not permit the calculations. The pH vs a curves for CuCdA and PdCdA complex systems do not sufficiently deviate from those of the 1 : 1, Cu^{II} -CAV and Pd^{II} -CAV system respectively, in pH range of $\text{MM}'\text{A}$ formation. A slight deviation of the curves (figures omitted) may be expected due to hydrolysis of Cd^{II} ion or any other interactions. In the attachment of Ni^{II} or Zn^{II} ion with CuH_2A and PdH_2A , lower value of equilibrium constants are obtained in systems with the latter complex. It is reasonably expected due to low electron density on the uncoordinated OH groups in the PdH_2A molecule which arises as a result of stronger electron-accepting nature of Pd^{II} than Cu^{II} as discussed earlier. Chelating behaviour of Zn^{II} is stronger than Ni^{II} in coordination with CuH_2A . Association of metal ions Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with PdH_2A follows the trend $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$.

Maximum %M associated with different species and the corresponding pH in 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 2 : 1, metal-ligand and $\text{MM}'\text{A}$ (1 : 1 : 1) mixed metal-ligand system were obtained (Table 2) from the distribution curves plotted between percentage metal distributed among various species and pH (Fig 2 Zn^{II} -CAV system, others omitted). Fig 2 shows that a progressive decrease in percentage of free Zn^{II} ion is accompanied by an increase in pH in all the system. In 1 : 1 Zn^{II} -CAV system, amount of free metal is insignificant beyond pH ~9.0 where practically all metal ion is coordinated in different complex species. At the same time formation of ZnH_2A occurs, it increases up to pH ~6.2, then decreases and finally becomes negligible at pH ~9.2. Ap-

preciable quantities of ZnH_2A , $ZnHA$, ZnA , respectively, lie in the pH range 4.6–9.0, 5.9–10.2, 7.8–..... with the maximum percentage 57.50 (pH ~6.2), 92.52 (pH ~7.8), 80.02 (pH ~10.2). Gradual decrease in free metal percentage with increase of pH is also visible in case of 1 : 2, Zn^{II} -CAV system. Above pH ~7.8, it becomes negligible due to formation of 1 : 2 species. Thus the whole of the metal ion is associated with the ligand in the form of ZnH_2A , $Zn(H_2A)_2$, $Zn(H_2A)HA$, $Zn(HA)_2$, $Zn(HA)A$. Maximum percentage of ZnH_2A , $Zn(H_2A)_2$, $Zn(H_2A)HA$, $Zn(HA)_2$, $Zn(HA)A$ formed in mixture are : 46.85, 49.00, 69.40, 80.20, 75.99 respectively; pH 5.0–9.2, 5.0–9.2, 6.4–10.2, 7.2–....., 9.2–....., being the corresponding range of pH of their existence. In 2 : 1, Zn^{II} -CAV mixture, formation of Zn_2A takes place from pH ~6.0. Maximum amount of Zn_2A present in solution has been recorded as 81.11% at pH 7.0.

Experimental

Stock solution of 0.1306 N NaOH was prepared. Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} were determined by EDTA titration and Pd^{II} was estimated gravimetrically using dimethylglyoxime as precipitating reagent⁸.

Procedure : The following aqueous mixtures were prepared and titrated against NaOH solution (0.1306 N) using a EC 5652 pH meter with combined electrode system : (i) HNO_3 ; (ii) $5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ ligand + (i); (iii) $5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ metal ion + (ii); (iv) $2.5 \times 10^{-4} M$ metal ion + (ii); (v) $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ metal ion + (ii). In case of M-M'-A type of species, mixtures containing ligand and pair of metal ions (Cu^{II} - Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} - Zn^{II} , Cu^{II} - Cd^{II} , Pd^{II} - Cu^{II} , Pd^{II} - Ni^{II} , Pd^{II} - Zn^{II} and Pd^{II} - Cd^{II}) in 1 : 1 : 1 ratio (each $5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$) were also prepared and titrated pH-metrically at 25°. Initial volume of each mixture was kept at 50 cm³ at an ionic strength of 0.1 M (KNO_3). Calculations were done by the procedure

already described⁷ for furnishing informations on metal-ligand interactions.

References

1. J CACHO, A. LOPEZMOLINERO and J. E. CASTELLS, *Analyst (London)*, 1987, 112, 1723; M FERRIS and M. A. LEONARD, *Analyst (London)*, 1986, 111, 315, L. L. KOLOMIETS, O V. LYSLNKO and I. V. PYATNITSKII, *Zh Anal Khim.*, 1988, 43, 1773 C. SARZANINI, E. MENTASTI, M. C. CENNARO, V. PORTA and P. VOLPE, *Talanta* 1986, 33, 835; N. YONFHARA, T. YAMANE, T. TOMIYASU and H SAKAMOTO, *Anal Sci.*, 1989, 5, 175.
2. N. M. ALYKOV, *Antibiot Med Biotechnol.*, 1985, 30, 501 M JAROSZ and M. MALAT, *Microchem J.*, 1988, 37, 268, V KRISHNAREDDY and D. VENKATAREDDY, *Indian J Chem Sect A*, 1982, 21, 215; M. OMAR and H. J. M. BOWEN, *Analyst (London)*, 1982, 107, 654.
3. L. JANCAR, J. HAVEL and L. SOMMER, *Czech Chem Commun.* 1988, 53, 1424; R P LASTOVSKY, N. M. DYAILOVA and I A SELIVERSTOVA, *Zh Neorg Khim.* 1967, 12, 12, 3351 R J MOTEKAITIS and A. E. MARTELL, *J Am Chem Soc.*, 1970 92 4233; *Inorg Chem.*, 1974, 13, 558, R. NAYAN, A. K. PANDEY and SABHAPATI, "Proceedings of Asian Chemical Conference" Singapur. 1985; L. J. ZOMPA and R. F. BOGUICK, *J Am Chem Soc.*, 1969, 91, 4569.
4. E. A. BIRYUK and R. V. RAVITSKAYA, *Zh Anal Khim.* 1970, 25 8, 1643.
5. E. CHIACCHIERINI, G. D. ANGFLIS and P COCCANARI, *Gazz Chim Ital.*, 1973, 103, 413; R YU YURGAVICHUS and CH A VALYUKYAVICHYLS, *Zh Anal Khim.*, 1972, 27, 6, 1125.
6. D. D. PERRIN, "Stability Constants of Metal Ion Complexes", Pergamon, New York, 1979; W. D. WAKLEY and L P VARGA *Anal Chim.*, 1972, 44, 169.
7. R. NAYAN, *J Inorg Nucl Chem.*, 1980, 42, 1743, 1981, 43 383 R. NAYAN and A. K. DEY, *Indian J Chem Sect A*, 1976 14, 892
8. "Vogel's Textbook of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", eds J BASSETT, R. C DENNEY, G. H. JEFFERY and J MENDHAN Longmans, London, 1978.